

Stress and Strength Analysis of Composite Laminates at Delamination

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ABSTRACT

A stress and strength analysis of composite laminates built of anisotropic layers of uniform thickness and subjected to prescribed tractions/displacements on its boundary surfaces have been conducted. A global-local model developed for this class of problems has been used to conduct the stress analysis of the laminate. Three-dimensional stress and in-plane strength predictions are given for pure graphite and hybrid laminates. The onset of delamination in pure graphite laminates has been investigated on the basis of an average stress failure criterion in conjunction with the σ_z calculations by global-local model. The available experimental results show a close agreement with the predictions.

INTRODUCTION

The key to the reliable and optimum use of composite materials is to understand their exact stress and strength characteristics. These characteristics are highly sensitive to the ply orientation and the stacking sequence in the laminate. The sensitivity analysis with the parametric changes is an important element in the evolution of dependable and cost-effective structures. To achieve these objectives a number of analytical tools have been developed (1,2,3). In reference (1), a theory called "Global-Local Model" has been developed to conduct three-dimensional stress analysis of thick composite laminates and is based upon a variational principle. This model employs the Reissner functional, an approach developed by Pagano (2) for layered media, in a region of interest-local domain, and the potential energy, corresponding to Whitney-Sun theory (4), elsewhere-global domain. The effectiveness of the global-local model was demonstrated through the use of numerical examples in (1) and (4) and experimental verification of the stress and strength predictions in (4,5). These studies were conducted for a free-edge class of boundary value problems in composite laminates.

In the present paper, the global-local model has been employed to conduct the stress and strength analysis of pure T300/5208 graphite-epoxy laminates and hybrid-graphite/Kevlar laminates. Here again the free-edge class of boundary value problems is considered. The significant three-dimensional stress components are computed for a large number of composite laminates. On the basis of the tensor polynomial failure criterion (6), failure surfaces for some of the

laminates are given. The onset of delamination predictions are made on the basis of an average stress failure criterion (7) and agree closely with the experimental findings.

PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

Figure 1 shows the laminate geometry. The laminate is symmetric about the midplane and is made of orthotropic layers. The x-axis is along the width of the laminate. A uniaxial strain $\epsilon_y = \epsilon$ is applied at the laminate edge. All stresses are functions of x and z in this class of problems. The significant stress components are computed by using the global-local model in the free-edge region ($b - h/2 \leq x \leq b$) of the laminate, where 2b is the width and h is the total thickness of the laminate. The following normalizations are used:

$$x = \frac{x - b - h/2}{h/2}$$

$$z = \frac{2z}{h}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following laminates have been investigated in detail:

$$(0_n/90_{8-n})_s \quad n = 1,2,3,4$$

and

$$(0/(\pm 60)_m)_s \quad m = 1,2,6,10$$

The laminate orientation notation used here is such that the first ply mentioned in the notation represents the first ply above the mid-surface of the laminate. The laminates made of pure T300/5208 graphite-epoxy and hybrid T300/5208 and Kevlar 49 aramid-epoxy materials are studied. In hybrid laminates 0° plies are of

Fig. 1: Laminate Geometry.

Kevlar material, whereas the other plies are of T300/5208 material. The material properties of the two composite materials are:

T300/5208 graphite-epoxy

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{11} &= 21.0 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & , & \quad E_{22} = E_{33} = 1.6 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} \\
 G_{12} = G_{13} &= 0.8 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & , & \quad G_{23} = 0.6 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} \\
 \nu_{12} = \nu_{13} &= 0.25 & , & \quad \nu_{23} = 0.6 \\
 S_{11}^T &= 210 \text{ ksi} & , & \quad S_{11}^C = 210 \text{ ksi} \\
 S_{22}^T &= 7.5 \text{ ksi} & , & \quad S_{22}^C = 30 \text{ ksi} \\
 S_{12} &= 13.5 \text{ ksi}
 \end{aligned}$$

Kevlar 49 aramid-epoxy

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{11} &= 11.02 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & , & \quad E_{22} = E_{33} = 0.8 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} \\
 G_{12} = G_{13} &= 0.33 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & , & \quad G_{23} = 0.25 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} \\
 \nu_{12} = \nu_{13} &= 0.34 & , & \quad \nu_{23} = 0.53 \\
 S_{11}^T &= 203 \text{ ksi} & , & \quad S_{11}^C = 34.1 \text{ ksi} \\
 S_{22}^T &= 1.74 \text{ ksi} & , & \quad S_{22}^C = 7.69 \text{ ksi} \\
 S_{12} &= 4.93 \text{ ksi}
 \end{aligned}$$

where E, G, and ν denote, respectively, the Young's modulus, the shear modulus, and the major Poisson's ratio. S denotes the in-plane strength of the material. The subscripts 1, 2, 3 correspond to the directions x, y, z, respectively, the superscript T and C correspond to the tensile and compressive strengths, respectively. It is assumed that $b \rightarrow \infty$.

Figures 2-5 give the stress components $\sigma_z(X,0)$, $\sigma_z(X,Z_i)$ and $\tau_{xz}(X,Z_i)$ for four laminates, $(0/90)_S$, $(04/904)_S$, $(0/\pm 60)_S$ and $(0/(\pm 60)_{10})_S$, where Z_i denotes the value of Z at the 0/90 or 0/60 interface. Tables 1 and 2 give the peak values of these stress components for all the laminates. Figures 6-9 depict the in-plane failure surfaces for some of the laminates in stress space based upon the tensor polynomial failure criterion using LMTAN (3). Since Figures 2-5 give the results due to an applied strain $\epsilon_y = \epsilon$, the required effective in-plane material properties of corresponding laminates are presented in Table 3. Table 4 gives the stress and strength predictions and experimental results for a large number of laminates made of pure graphite material.

Figure 2 depicts the stress components for $(0/90)_S$ laminates - 2(a) for pure graphite material and 2(b) for hybrid one. There are extraneous humps in these figures for $\sigma_z(X,0)$ near the edge, which are due to insufficient subdivisions of the layers in the local domain. The peak values are close to the converged result for the free edge stress. On comparison we see that in the hybrid laminate all the stress components are considerably lower than those for the pure graphite laminate. Thus, the hybrid laminate will resist delamination more than the pure graphite laminate. Table 1 shows a comparison of peak stress values between the pure graphite and the hybrid laminates. The maximum and the minimum percentage difference between the results for two material systems are also given. In all the four cases, the stress components in the hybrid laminates are more than 24% lower than those in the pure graphite laminates. A comparison of in-plane strengths between the pure graphite and the hybrid laminate $(0/90)_S$ is given in Figure 6. There is only about 1% difference in the effective Young's modulus E_{22}^o between the two types of laminates. For transverse loading first-ply strength in the hybrid laminate is reduced to about one-half of the first-ply strength of the pure graphite laminate and the last ply strengths remain the same. A similar behavior is observed in $(04/904)_S$, $(0/\pm 60)_S$ and $(0/(\pm 60)_{10})_S$ laminates in Figures 3-5 and 7-9.

TABLE 1
PEAK STRESSES IN PSI FOR DIFFERENT LAMINATES

Laminate	System	$\sigma_z(1,0)$	$\sigma_z(1,Z_1)$	$\tau_{xz}(\Delta, Z_1)$	Δ
		$\epsilon 10^5$	$\epsilon 10^5$	$\epsilon 10^5$	
$(0_1/90_7)_s$	T300/5208	6.47	6.56	3.31	.05
	Hybrid	4.64	2.54 (2.76) ⁺	2.37	.05
$(0_2/90_6)_s$	T300/5208	5.55	5.65	3.11	.05
	Hybrid	3.95	1.72 (2.20) ⁺	2.23	.05
$(0_3/90_5)_s$	T300/5208	4.21	4.90	2.9	.05
	Hybrid	3.07	1.25 (1.56) ⁺	2.09	.05
$(0/90)_s$	T300/5208	3.07	4.3	2.70	.05
	Hybrid	2.31	1.0 (1.25) ⁺	1.97	.05
Max % Difference		28.0	71.0	28	
Min % Difference		25.0	58.0	27	

$\Delta = 1 - X_p$, X_p is the value of X where peak occurs.

+ = peak value; extraneous hump.

TABLE 2
PEAK STRESSES IN PSI FOR DIFFERENT LAMINATES

Laminate	System	$\sigma_z(1,0)$	$\sigma_z(1,Z_1)$	$\tau_{xz}(\Delta, Z_1)$	Δ
		$\epsilon 10^5$	$\epsilon 10^5$	$\epsilon 10^5$	
$(0/\pm 60)_s$	T300/5208	34.23	32.03	14.57	.1
	Hybrid	24.24	12.81	11.14	.2
$(0/(\pm 60)_2)_s$	T300/5208	47.45	43.82	17.43	.1
	Hybrid	29.57	16.19	12.23	.15
$(0/(\pm 60)_6)_s$	T300/5208	52.65	47.48	17.11	.05
	Hybrid	32.12	16.26	11.48	.05
$(0/(\pm 60)_{10})_s$	T300/5208	69.06	59.41	25.28	.05
	Hybrid	40.58	18.08	17.70	.05
Max % Difference		41	70	33	
Min % Difference		29	60	24	

$\Delta = 1 - X_p$, X_p is the value of X where peak occurs.

In Table 4 applied strain ϵ corresponds to the strain at which the onset of delamination occurs (8), $\bar{\sigma}_z$ is the calculated average stress $\sigma_z(X,0)$ over a distance h_0 - a ply thickness, σ is the calculated applied laminate stress and in-plane strengths denote the successive ply failure strengths on the basis of tensor polynomial failure criterion (6). It has been observed experimentally as well as through predictions that in almost all these laminates, the first-ply failure occurs before the onset of delamination. On the basis of the average

TABLE 3
SOME EFFECTIVE IN-PLANE ENGINEERING CONSTANTS IN 10^6 PSI FOR DIFFERENT LAMINATES

Laminate	System	E_{11}°	E_{22}°	ν_{21}°
$(0/90_7)_S$	T300/5208	4.04	18.65	.021
	Hybrid	2.78	18.54	.021
$(0_4/90_4)_S$	T300/5208	11.35	11.35	.035
	Hybrid	6.35	10.95	.031
	Max % Difference	44.1	3.5	0
	Min % Difference	31.2	0.6	11.4
$(0/\pm 60)_S$	T300/5208	8.19	8.19	.3
	Hybrid	4.86	7.48	.3
$(0/(\pm 60)_{10})_S$	T300/5208	2.69	8.55	.3
	Hybrid	2.21	8.01	.3
	Max % Difference	40.7	8.7	0
	Min % Difference	11.8	6.3	0

TABLE 4
STRESS AND STRENGTH ANALYSIS AT DELAMINATION FOR PURE GRAPHITE LAMINATES

Laminate	Applied ϵ %	$\bar{\sigma}_z$	Applied Laminate σ (ksi)	Inplane Strengths (ksi)
$(0/90/\pm 45)_S$.52	7.9	40.5	21.7, 39.5, 75.0
$(0/\pm 45/90)_S$.66	8.1	51.4	21.7, 39.5, 75.0
$(0_2/\pm 45_2/90_2)_S$.54	9.0	42.1	21.7, 39.5, 75.0
$(0/\pm 75/90)_S$.68	7.6	96.0	37.6, 113.0, 121.1
$(0/\pm 60/90)_S$.55	9.2	59.6	29.0, 78.3, 104.2
$(0/\pm 60)_S$.39	8.4	30.4	21.7, 56.3
$(0/\pm 60_2)_S$.33	9.0	28.2	22.9, 69.5
$(0/\pm 60_4)_S$.26	8.7	22.4	22.3, 76.1
$(0/\pm 60_6)_S$.22	7.7	18.7	21.3, 76.1
$(\pm 30/\pm 60)_S$.61	8.4	34.68	21.7, 46.6
$(\pm 30_2/\pm 60_2)_S$.53	8.9	29.75	21.7, 46.6
$(0_2/\pm 60_2)_S$.36	9.2	27.7	21.7, 56.3
$(0_4/\pm 60_4)_S$.25	7.7	19.46	21.7, 56.3
$(0_3/\pm 45/90_3)_S$.35	7.0	27.33	21.7, 39.5, 75.0
$(0_3/\pm 45/90)_S$.67	9.6	40.61	17.5, 28.2, 50.4
$(0_6/\pm 45/90)_S$.54	5.6	24.66	14.1, 21.5, 36.6
$(\pm 45/0/90)_S$	-.66	6.6	-51.76	-(53, 121, 151)
$(\pm 45/0_3/90)_S$	-.68	8.3	-40.67	-(51, 106, 126)
$(\pm 45/0_6/90)_S$	-.78	9.4	-35.37	-(41, 84, 97)

stress failure criterion the $\bar{\sigma}_z$ corresponds to the transverse strength of the material used, which is about 7.5 ksi. Thus, the average stress failure criterion in conjunction with the global-local model calculations gives predictions close to the experimental results.

CONCLUSION

Global-local model has been used to calculate the three-dimensional response of composite laminates for a unidirectional applied load. All the significant stress components in hybrid laminates are above 24% less than those in pure graphite laminates. The in-plane first-ply strengths of hybrid laminates are reduced to one-half of the pure graphite laminate first-ply strength. The last ply failure strengths in both types of laminates remain almost the same. For the onset of delamination, the average stress failure criterion in conjunction with the global-local model stress predictions gives results close to the experimental results.

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Fig. 2: Stress Distribution in a $(0/90)_7$ Laminate.

Fig. 3: Stress Distribution in a $(0/90)_8$ Laminate.

Fig. 4: Stress Distribution in a $(0/\pm 60)_3$ Laminate.

Fig. 5: Stress Distribution in a $(0/(\pm 60)_{10})_s$ Laminate. GLBL represents the global domain.

Fig. 6: Failure Surfaces for a $(0/90_7)_S$ Laminate.

Fig. 7: Failure Surfaces for a $(0/90)_S$ Laminate.

Fig. 8: Failure Surfaces for a $(0/\pm 60)_S$ Laminate.

Fig. 9: Failure Surfaces for a $(0/(+60)_{10})_S$ Laminate.